

ASSURANCE AND CUSTOMER PATRONAGE OF MICROFINANCE BANKS IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The objective of this study was to examine the influence of assurance on Customer patronage of Microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State. To achieve this objective, the main source of data was through primary sources with the use of a questionnaire. The researcher adopted the survey research design approach and data were collected from 323 respondents drawn from the banks customers' base. A total number of 295 copies of the questionnaire were retrieved in useable form representing 91.3 percent of data analyzed using the Simple Regression Model (SRM). Data generated from the study were processed using descriptive and inferential statistics and hypothesis tested at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that assurance had significant influence on customer patronage of Microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State. Thus, the study recommended that the managers of Microfinance banks should employ employees who have the knowledge, courtesy and ability to convey trust and confidence in their customers, making their customers feel safe in their transactions so that their perceived service will exceed their expected service in order to enhance good customer patronage.*

Keywords: *Assurance, Service Quality, Customer Patronage, Microfinance Banks.*

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Services must be adapted to the constantly changing business environment. Presently, the redesigned naira, new withdrawal limits, and the scarcity of naira notes in circulation have caused a significant influx of both existing and potential customers to banks, all demanding efficient, prompt, and high-quality service (Etuk, Awah, and Akpan, 2024).

On an international scale, the banking industry has become highly competitive, with deposit money banks vying for customers from Microfinance banks. The rise of new deposit money banks and new Microfinance banks has resulted in customers becoming more discerning and demanding better service quality (Osim, Muyanja, and Bainyana, 2020). Consequently, banking firms are leveraging technology to differentiate their service offerings in an increasingly competitive market (Osim et al., 2020). Self-

service technologies such as automated teller machines, online/internet banking, telephone banking, mobile banking, and SMS banking are being utilized to meet customers' banking needs. These technologies offer convenience, transaction security, ease of use, quality information delivery, and reliability (Osim et al., 2020; Akpan, 2007).

Superior technology coupled with excellent service quality enables bank customers to make online purchases via the banks' online banking platforms. Chattopadhyay (2019) asserts that the success of Microfinance Banks (MFB) primarily hinges on customer satisfaction. In thriving business organizations, customers are prioritized over profits. Therefore, MFBs should align their service quality with monetary value to attract and sustain long-term relationships with customers, which will result in an increase in both existing and potential customer numbers and improved customer patronage (Chattopadhyay, 2019). Okeke (2020) considers customer patronage to be a crucial factor for enhancing bank profits and maintaining the banks' competitive position.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Research indicates that increasing liquidation rates among microfinance banks where a bank is established and ceases operations within a few years along with poor reputations, lack of customer satisfaction, excessive account charges, and poor crisis management, have significantly undermined public confidence in these institutions, thus impacting customer patronage (Agbele; Onoriode, 2021; Etuk, Awah, and Akpan, 2022).

Customers frequently encounter unreliable technology services when using ATMs, often finding machines out of service or lacking sufficient cash. Additionally, clients attempting to access funds via mobile banking face challenges due to process complexity; for instance, mobile applications are only compatible with Android phones, and the short session time of USSD services makes them inconvenient for some users (Akpan and Abdul, 2009; Osinde, Mayanja, and Tibaingana, 2020).

Unfortunately, while there have been numerous studies on the activities of Microfinance Banks (e.g., Akpan, 2007; Acha, 2012; Wardhana and Satriyanto, 2020; Alshammari, Mahmond, and Daud, 2021; Njagi and Njoku, 2021), there has been minimal focus on service quality and customer patronage in developing economies like Nigeria. Furthermore, most research on financial institutions has centered on deposit money banks, with little attention given to Microfinance Banks, particularly in Nigeria (Cai, Park, and Wang, 2016). This evident knowledge gap serves as the primary motivation for conducting this study.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the influence of assurance on customer patronage of selected Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State.

1.4 Research Question

This study attempts to provide answers to the following question.

➤ What is the influence of assurance on customer patronage of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State?

1.5 Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was postulated to guide the study:

➤ Assurance does not significantly influence customer patronage of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study is of immense value to government, bank regulators, investors, academics and other stakeholders. It will go a long way in contributing to the growth of businesses in many aspects like increase in the volume of sales, return on investment and maintenance of goodwill. By identifying the strength of some Microfinance Banks, it will aid in restoring public confidence in the Microfinance banks leading to a positive social change in our society. This study will enable the government to know the problems affecting Microfinance banks and realize how difficult the porches are and device a means of solving the problems. It will aid the government to know how to uplift the image of Microfinance Banks in Nigeria. Above all, by addressing sustainability challenge of Microfinance banks it will help to generate employment as there may be stronger and viable microfinance banks in Nigeria.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The scope of the study covered the following three central aspects:

Content Scope: The content scope of this study covered the service quality variable used by Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State such as assurance and customer patronage. It also covers the concepts on service quality and customer patronage. This study was domiciled in service and strategic marketing.

Geographical Scope: The geographical scope of the study was in Akwa Ibom State located at the South South region of Nigeria.

Unit of Analysis: The unit of analysis of this study involved customers of the selected Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State, namely: Uniuyo microfinance bank, Palmcoast microfinance bank, Active point microfinance bank, Eduek microfinance bank ,Ikpe-Annang microfinance banks, Ini microfinance bank, Madelyn microfinance bank, Nsehe microfinance bank and Akcofed microfinance bank.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Concept of Service Quality

Service quality refers to the extent to which the provided service meets customer expectations. To enhance profits and market share, banks must prioritize the services they offer to customers (Chattopadhyay, 2019). The relative superiority of a bank and its services is reflected in service quality,

making it crucial for the survival of all service-oriented companies (Chattopadhyay, 2019).

Service quality is perceived as an attitude; maintaining and improving it is a continuous effort for banks aiming for long-term customer satisfaction (Chattopadhyay, 2019). Retaining the right customers through high service quality is essential. Therefore, banks should focus on retaining profitable customers and building customer equity. Service quality can provide a competitive advantage and differentiate a bank from its competitors. High-quality service can attract potential customers and retain existing ones (Darmawan, Mardikaningsih, and Hadi, 2017).

Zebrega and Zaveri (2020) examined the impact of service quality on customer loyalty in Ethiopian hotels. Their findings indicated that tangibility and reliability both had positive and statistically significant relationships with customer loyalty.

Darmawan et al. (2017) found that service quality had a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction, corporate image, and customer loyalty in the Indonesian banking sector. They argued that service quality could enhance customer patronage and the corporate image within the banking industry.

2.1.2 Customer Patronage

A bank that attracts a substantial number of customers who utilize its services is deemed successful. Banks aim to cultivate satisfied customers who return for additional transactions (Anetoh, 2016; Etuk, Awah, and Akpan, 2024). Customer satisfaction is a key factor in encouraging repeat usage of services, although a satisfied customer may not always return (Nnamdi, 2020). Therefore, banks must provide quality services to build goodwill and attract consistent customer patronage (Anetoh, 2016).

Smith (2012) offers five strategies to ensure ongoing customer patronage: building strong personal relationships with customers, avoiding rudeness, maintaining integrity, rewarding customer loyalty, and contributing value to society. These strategies can enhance service quality, leading to improved customer satisfaction and continued patronage.

Rahman, Hossain, Zaman, and Mannan (2020) found that customer trust significantly mediates the relationship between e-service quality and customers' patronage intentions. The adoption of advanced technology significantly moderates the relationship between trust and patronage intention in the context of online retail banking.

Anetoh (2016), in his study on service quality dimensions and customer patronage of grocery services in Nigeria, revealed a significant relationship between these dimensions and customer patronage. He also identified the SERVPERF model as a useful tool for measuring service quality and customer patronage in Nigerian grocery services.

2.1.3 SERVICE QUALITY GAP

Kotler and Armstrong (2020) propose the existence of five gaps that contribute to unsuccessful service delivery, detailed as follows:

One such gap arises when management does not accurately understand customer desires. For instance, a bank might believe customers prioritize loan availability, whereas customers might actually value staff responsiveness more. Another gap occurs when management correctly identifies customer needs but fails to establish the necessary performance standards to meet those needs.

A third gap can emerge when employees are inadequately trained, incapable, or unwilling to meet the set standards, often due to conflicting priorities, such as balancing listening to customers with providing fast service. Additionally, customer expectations can be influenced by company representatives and advertisements; if promotional materials depict an elegant banking hall, but customers find it to be cheap and unimpressive, external communications have misled their expectations.

Finally, a gap can exist when there is a discrepancy between the service quality customers perceive and what they initially expected.

2.1.4 Assurance and Customer Patronage

Assurance involves the knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to convey trust and confidence. Kim and Park (2013) studied the relationship between service quality, trust, and customer loyalty in social commerce. They found that service quality positively influences trust, which subsequently affects customer loyalty. They suggested that businesses in social commerce should enhance service quality and build trust to foster customer loyalty.

In their study on the effect of service quality on customer loyalty within Ethiopian hotels, Zebrega and Zaveri (2020) discovered that hotel customers exhibit loyalty when employees respond promptly to their requests, make customers feel secure in their transactions, provide individual attention, and understand customer needs. They concluded that service quality variables such as tangibility, responsiveness, reliability, assurance, and empathy positively influence customer loyalty. Hence, hotel managers should effectively leverage these variables to gain a competitive advantage.

Lin and Chang (2022) examined the effects of e-service quality on customer satisfaction and repurchase intention in online apparel shopping. They found that e-service quality significantly impacts both customer satisfaction and repurchase intention. They recommended that online apparel retailers should prioritize improving e-service quality to boost customer satisfaction and encourage repeat purchases.

Liu and Shi (2022) investigated the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and purchase intention in online grocery shopping. Their findings indicated that service quality significantly affects customer satisfaction and purchase intention. They advised online grocery retailers to focus on enhancing service quality to increase customer satisfaction and drive purchase behavior.

Chen and Li (2022) explored the role of e-service quality in customer retention on e-commerce platforms. They concluded that e-service quality plays a crucial role in retaining customers and

fostering long-term loyalty. They recommended that e-commerce platforms should concentrate on providing high-quality e-services to retain customers and enhance their loyalty over time.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

In this section one major theory was considered relevant for this study; this include;

2.2.2 Service Performance (SERVPERF) Model Propounded by Cronin, J. and Taylor, S. (1992)

The SERVPERF model measures quality as an attitude rather than satisfaction. Thus, the model uses the idea of perceived service quality which leads to satisfaction. The model then connects satisfaction with further purchase intentions. The SERVPERF model is a modification of SERVQUAL and uses the same dimensions of SERVQUAL to assess service quality which include the following; tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy and they proposed a 22 performance items related. This model is used in the banking industry to measure customer service performance. Banks uses this model to evaluate how quickly their customers are assisted, how transactions are accurately processed, and how the banks stuffs are helpful when customers have questions.

2.3 Review of Empirical Studies

This section is concerned with the review of the studies which were considered to be relevant, accordingly 13 studies were reviewed.

2.3.1 Lin and Chang (2022): Assessing the Effects of E-service Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Repurchase Intention: A Study of Online Apparel Shopping. The objective of the study was to assess the effects of e-service quality on customer satisfaction and repurchase intention in the context of online apparel shopping. The online survey data was analyzed using regression analysis. The study showed that E-service quality significantly impacts customer satisfaction and repurchase intention. The study recommended that online apparel retailers should prioritize improving e-service quality to increase customer satisfaction and encourage repurchase behavior. Critics: The study successfully assesses the effects of e-service quality on customer satisfaction and repurchase intention in online apparel shopping, but further investigation into the underlying factors affecting these relationships would strengthen its practical implications.

2.3.2 Huang and Hsieh (2022): The Influence of Service Quality on Customer Loyalty in Mobile Food Delivery Apps: A Study of Millennials. The study objective is to investigate the influence of service quality on customer loyalty in mobile food delivery apps, specifically among Millennials Survey questionnaire were administered to Millennials using mobile food delivery apps. The result showed that Service quality significantly influences customer loyalty. It recommended that Mobile food delivery app providers should focus on enhancing service quality to cultivate customer loyalty among Millennials. Critics: The study explores the influence of service quality on customer loyalty in mobile food delivery

apps among Millennials, but further investigation into the specific service quality aspects that resonate with this demographic would enhance its practical relevance.

2.3.3 Wang et al. (2022): E-service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, and Loyalty in Online Travel Booking: A Study of Generation Z. The objective of the work is to examine the relationships between e-service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty in the context of online travel booking, particularly among Generation Z. The Online survey data were analyzed using structural equation modeling. The Result showed that E-service quality positively influences customer satisfaction and loyalty. It was recommended that online travel booking platforms should prioritize delivering high-quality e-services to satisfy Generation Z customers and foster their loyalty. Critics: The study effectively examines the relationships between e-service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty in online travel booking among Generation Z, but further research on the specific e-service quality attributes that drive satisfaction and loyalty would provide more actionable insights for online travel platforms.

2.3.4 Liu et al. (2022): The Impact of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Purchase Intention: A Study of Online Grocery Shopping. The study aimed at investigating the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and purchase intention in the context of online grocery shopping. The Survey data was analyzed using regression analysis. Result of the finding showed that service quality significantly impacts customer satisfaction and purchase intention. And it was recommended that online grocery retailers should prioritize improving service quality to increase customer satisfaction and encourage purchase behavior. Critics: While the study effectively investigated the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and purchase intention in the context of online grocery shopping, it could have been strengthened by incorporating qualitative methods to gain deeper insights into customer experiences and preferences.

2.3.5 Chen and Li (2022): Examining the Role of E-service Quality in Customer Retention: A Study of E-commerce Platforms. The study aimed at examining the role of e-service quality in customer retention within e-commerce platforms. Survey data was analyzed using structural equation modeling. The findings were that E-service quality plays a significant role in customer retention. It recommended that E-commerce platforms should focus on providing high-quality e-services to retain customers and increase their long-term loyalty. Critics: Although the study successfully examined the role of e-service quality in customer retention within e-commerce platforms, it would have been valuable to consider the potential moderating factors that could influence the relationship between e-service quality and customer retention

2.3.6 Jiang et al. (2022): Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, and Repurchase Intention in E-ticketing: A Study of Online Event Ticketing. The study aimed at investigating the relationships between service quality, customer satisfaction, and repurchase intention in the context of online event ticketing. Descriptive and inferential statistics was used for data analysis the findings were that service quality

positively influences customer satisfaction and repurchase intention. The recommendation was that online event ticketing platforms should prioritize improving service quality to enhance customer satisfaction and stimulate repurchase behavior. Critics: While the study provided useful insights into the relationships between service quality, customer satisfaction, and repurchase intention in online event ticketing, it lacked a longitudinal approach to assess how changes in service quality over time may impact customer behavior.

2.3.7 Zeithaml, Parasuraman and Malhotra (2002): The Role of Service Quality in Online Shopping Behavior. The objective of this study was to examine the role of service quality in online shopping behavior. The researchers employed a survey questionnaire administered to online shoppers to gather data. And the study found a positive correlation between service quality and online shopping behavior. Based on the results, the study recommends that online retailers should prioritize improving service quality to enhance online shopping behavior. Strategies to improve reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles should be implemented to meet customer expectations and increase customer satisfaction. Critics: The study's findings on the positive correlation between service quality and online shopping behavior were relevant, but the research could have included a comparison of different online retailers to identify specific service quality attributes that differentiate successful platforms from others.

2.3.8 Wolfinbarger and Gilly (2003): Measuring Service Quality in E-tailing. The objective of the study was to develop a measurement scale for assessing service quality in online retailing. Data for this study was collected through online surveys, and statistical techniques were used to analyze the data. And the study result successfully developed a reliable and valid service quality measurement scale. The study recommended the adoption of the developed measurement scale to evaluate and monitor service quality in e-tailing. Critics: The development of a measurement scale for assessing service quality in online retailing was commendable, but the study would have been more robust if it had included a validation phase to test the scale's effectiveness across different e-tailers and industries.

2.3.9 Yang, Peterson and Huang (2004): Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, and Customer Loyalty in E-commerce: A Structural Equation Modeling Approach. The study aimed to investigate the relationships between service quality, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty in e-commerce. The researchers' utilized structural equation modeling (SEM) applied to survey data to analyze the relationships between the variables. And the result of the study revealed that service quality positively affects customer satisfaction, which, in turn, influences customer loyalty. Based on the findings, the study recommended that e-commerce businesses should prioritize service quality improvements to enhance customer satisfaction and foster customer loyalty. Critics: While the study's use of structural equation modeling provided valuable insights into the relationships between service quality, customer

satisfaction, and customer loyalty in e-commerce, it lacked a qualitative component to better understand the underlying reasons behind the observed connections.

2.3.10 Suh and Han (2002): Effects of Perceived E-Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction, Trust, and Loyalty: The Case of Online Travel Websites. The objective of the study was to examine the effects of perceived e-service quality on customer satisfaction, trust, and loyalty, specifically focusing on online travel websites. The researchers analyzed survey data using structural equation modeling to explore the relationships between perceived e-service quality and the outcomes of customer satisfaction, trust, and loyalty. The result of the study found that perceived e-service quality positively influences customer satisfaction, trust, and loyalty. Based on the findings, the study suggests that online travel websites should focus on enhancing perceived e-service quality to improve customer satisfaction, trust, and loyalty. Critics: The study's focus on perceived e-service quality and its effects on customer satisfaction trust, and loyalty for online travel websites was relevant, but a comparative analysis of various travel websites with different e-service quality levels would have added more practical implications.

2.3.11 Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Malhotra (2005): Assessing the Dimensions of E-service Quality. The study aimed at assessing the dimensions of e-service quality. The researchers administered a survey questionnaire to online consumers to collect data for this study. The study successfully identified and assessed the dimensions of e-service quality, including reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. Based on the results, the study recommends that organizations delivering e-services should focus on enhancing the identified dimensions of e-service quality. Critics: The study's assessment of the dimensions of e-service quality was insightful, but it could have been further enhanced by exploring how these dimensions may vary across different cultural contexts and customer segments.

2.3.12 Lee and Lee (2020): Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, and Repurchase Intention in Online Food Delivery Services. The objective of the study is to investigate the relationships between service qualities, customer satisfaction, and repurchase intention in the context of online food delivery services. The survey data collected from online food delivery service users and analyzed using structural equation modeling. The result showed that service quality positively influences customer satisfaction, which in turn affects repurchase intention.

Based on the findings of this study, the recommendation was that online food delivery service providers should focus on improving service quality to enhance customer satisfaction and encourage repurchase intention. Critics: The study's investigation into the relationships between service quality, customer satisfaction, and repurchase intention in online food delivery services was valuable, but incorporating a control group of offline food delivery users would have strengthened the study's conclusions.

2.3.13 Raza, Standing and Standing (2019): Exploring the Impact of E-service Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Behavioral Intention: A Case of Online Banking Services.

The objective of the study is to explore the impact of e-service quality on customer satisfaction and behavioral intention in the context of online banking services. Online survey data collected from online banking customers and analyzed using regression analysis. The findings were that E-service quality significantly affects customer satisfaction and behavioral intention. The study recommended that banks should enhance the user interface and navigation of online banking platforms to make them more intuitive, user-friendly, and visually appealing. Critics: The study's exploration of the impact of e-service quality on customer satisfaction and behavioral intention in online banking services was significant, but it could have included qualitative interviews with customers to gain deeper insights into their perceptions and behaviors.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Design of the Study

The study design adopted by the researcher in this study was the Survey Research Design. Data on the independent variable and the dependent variable were collected from different microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State. The survey research design used assisted the researcher in reaching out to a good number of customers of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State. The justification for using the survey research design was to aid the researcher in gathering information from a good number of customers of Microfinance Banks in order to understand their opinions, attitudes, behaviours, or characteristics. It is useful for studying topics that can be measured quantitatively and for obtaining a wide range of data quickly. This design allows researchers to collect data from a diverse sample and analyze trends, correlations, or patterns within the data.

3.2 Population of the Study

The target population for the study comprised all customers of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State. Hence, the Population of the study was infinite,

3.3 Sampling and the Sample Size determination

Since the population size for the study was infinite, sample size for this study was determined using the Topman Formula at 5% level of tolerable error.

The formula is given as

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot pq}{e^2}$$

Where n = required sample size

z = the value of z-score associated with the degree of confidence is 95% confidence level being 1.96 from the Z-score table.

p = 0.7 decimal (positive)

q = 0.3 decimal (negative)

e = acceptable tolerance level of error (stated in percentage points)

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot pq}{e^2}$$

$$= \frac{1.96^2 \cdot (0.7 \times 0.3)}{}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{0.05^2}{\frac{3.8416 \times 0.21}{0.0025}} \\ &= \frac{0.806736}{0.0025} \\ &= 322.6 \\ &= 323 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the sample size of the study was 323.

3.4 Sampling Procedure

Convenient sampling technique was employed in the administration of the research instrument for this study. This was carried out by reaching out to the respondents based on their willingness to participate in the research as well as their accessibility and availability to the researcher. The total number of the research instrument (323) was divided by the total number of microfinance used in the study; this resulted in approximately 32 copies of questionnaire administered to each microfinance bank used in the study.

According to CBN (2020), there were 13 registered microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State. The researcher conducted a pilot study to ascertain which MFBs implemented the service quality dimension outlined in the study. The pilot study revealed that 10 MFBs indeed incorporated the specified service quality dimensions. Consequently, these dimensions were adopted and utilized in the present study.

1.

3.5 Methods of Data Collection

Data analysis involved both descriptive and inferential statistics. Data was analyzed using the simple regression analysis to determine the influence of service quality on customer patronage. The hypothesis was tested at $P > 0.05$ level of significance.

3.6 Sources of Data

The main source of data employed in this study was the primary data source. The primary data source was a structured questionnaire which was served on respondents. The questionnaire was made up of two sections: section "A" generated data on demography, while section "B" was made up of two sub-sections which were the independent variable (assurance) and the dependent variable (customer patronage). Hence, the ordinal scale used for this study were strongly agree, 4; agree, 3; disagree, 2; strongly disagree, 1; neutral, 0; to elicit responses from the respondents. The five points were employed to measure the dependent and the independent variables.

3.7 Psychometric Properties of the Instrument

a. Validity of the Instrument

The research instrument was subjected to validity test by the supervisor and other experts in the field of study. The relevance of each item in relation to the purpose of the study and the formulated

hypothesis was assessed independently by the supervisor. Then the researcher used all the other observations made by the Supervisor and other experts in preparing the final copy of the questionnaire.

b. Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the research instrument was conducted to ascertain the degree to which the instrument yields consistent result. Hence, it was conducted to ascertain whether the variables of the study consistently measured the factors intended. In this study the internal consistency reliability was adopted, a pre-test for internal consistency measure using Cronbach’s Alpha was employed for assessing the reliability of the research instrument. The purpose of reliability test was to further ascertain whether the internal consistency of the scales is indicative of the homogeneity of the construct items that measures the variables. In the process, the reliability for each of these scales was determined at a minimum threshold of 0.7 and above (Cronbach, 1951). Furthermore, the composite reliability (CR) for all constructs was above 0.70 (Serbetar and Sedlar, 2016).

The obtained coefficients were:

S/No	NO.of items	Study Variables	Cronbach’s Alpha	Composite Reliability
1	3	Assurance	0.831	0.948
2	3	Customer Patronage	0.787	0.815

Source Author’s computation (2024)

In this study, the Cronbach alpha for all the construct ranges from 0.831 to 0.948. All the constructs had Cronbach Alpha greater than 0.70 thresholds. Furthermore, the overall Cronbach Alpha coefficient for the instrument was 0.877, which suggest that the instrument used for the evaluation was reliable. (Cronbach’s Alpha > 0.70). In addition, composite reliability of reflective items were all above the acceptable 0.7 threshold which means that all the variables in the study displayed construct reliability. All construct were viewed to have acceptable reliability levels because the composite reliability scores for all construct were above the 0.7 threshold.

3.8 Instrument Administration

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire with a 5 point Likert Scale ranging from 5 (Strongly agreed) to 1 (Strongly disagree). This consisted of Section A and Section B. Section A presented respondents personal data such as the age distribution of the respondents ranging from 18 to 50 years and above, gender distribution of the respondents divided into male and female, educational level segmented into SSCE, Diploma, HND/B.Sc, Masters and Ph.D, marital status of the respondents made up of single, married and divorced while section B presented questions on assurance with 3 questions and customer patronage with 3 questions.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Data Analysis

Test of Hypothesis One

Hypothesis 1

Hypothesis Assurance does not significantly influence customer patronage of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4.1.1 Model Summary of the Influence of Assurance on Customer patronage of Microfinance Banks

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std.Error of the Estimate
1	.790 ^a	.624	.623	1.92888

a. Predictors (constant), Assurance

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Analysis of Variance of the influence of Assurance on Customer Patronage of Microfinance Banks

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	1810.464	1	1810.464	486.607	.000 ^b
1 Residual	1090.133	293	3.721		
Total	2900.597	294			

a. **Dependent Variable:** Customer Patronage

b. **Predictors:** (Constant), Assurance

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Coefficients^a of the influence of Assurance on Customer Patronage of Microfinance Banks

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.457	.351		6.990	.000
	AssuranceTotal	.810	.037	.790	22.059	.000

a. Dependent Variable: PatronageTotal

The result in table 4.1.1 shows that there is a positive relationship between the independent and the dependent variable with R-value of (.790). The R-square which is the coefficient of determination is (.624). This is an indication of the independent variable (Assurance) in predicting the percentage of influence on the dependent variable (Customer Patronage). In other words, 62.4 percent of the variation in the dependent variable can be explained from the independent variable. The F-ratio value in the ANOVA table is 486.607 which is significant at 0.000, Since the probability value (0.000) is less

than 0.05 percent of significance. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative that Assurance actually contributes to the Customer Patronage of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State.

4.2 Discussion of Findings

The first hypothesis of this study states that assurance does not significantly influence customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State. The statistical analysis of data in table 4.1.1 indicated significant effect of Assurance on customer patronage of Microfinance Banks. This is in consonance with Rahman, et al., (2020) which showed that customer's trust plays a significant role in mediating the relationship between e- service quality and customer's patronage intention. This is in contrast with the study of Molae, et al. (2013) who found out that Assurance did not have positive and significant impact on customer satisfaction.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Summary

The main thrust of this study has been presented in the preceding four sections. This section is concerned with the summary of the study. The study investigated the influence of Assurance on Customer Patronage of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State. One hypothesis was formulated to guide this study and the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance through the use of simple regression analysis.

The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. This resulted from the fact that the regression result was significant, the computed F-value for the hypothesis show statistical significance of the overall regression model, this means that there was statistical significant effect of Service Quality variable (ie, Assurance) on customer patronage of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State.

To achieve the objective, a survey research design was used to reach out to the respondents of the Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State.. The population of the study was infinite. The Topman sample size determination formula at 5% level of tolerable error was used to determine the sample size of 323. The convenience sampling technique was employed in the administration of the research instrument for the study.

5.2 Conclusion

The study made the following conclusion.

i. Assurance has significant influence on Customer Patronage of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State.

This means that for every unit that Service Quality variable (ie, Assurance) increases, Customer Patronage of Microfinance Banks will also increase.

5.3 Recommendations

The conclusion of this study revealed that assurance has significant influence on Customer Patronage

of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State. Consequently, the study recommends that the managers of Microfinance banks should employ employees who have the knowledge, courtesy and ability to convey trust and confidence in their customers, making their customers feel safe in their transactions so that their perceived service will exceed their expected service in order to enhance good customer patronage. This is in consonance with the recommendations of Alafashat and Alofa (2018). They recommended that the bank management should provide periodical training for their employees to improve their skills and know-how to be able to solve customers' problems and meet customer satisfaction. This is also in consonance with the recommendations of Okeke and Okoye (2021), they recommended that the bank managers should enhance regular and timely training and retraining for their employees to improve their skills to solve customers' problems in order to enhance good customer patronage.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

This study has contributed to the body of knowledge in expanding the academic understanding of service quality within the context of microfinance, contributing to validating existing theories and frameworks in service marketing. Specifically, it has contributed in bridging the knowledge gap in literature with respect to Nigerian business environment by providing empirical evidence on the influence of service quality on customer patronage of microfinance banks particularly in Nigeria. The study findings revealed significant effect of service quality variable (ie, Assurance) on customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State. This is a novel discovery within the Nigerian banking environment, judging from findings of previous studies.

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